

A Brief History of Economic Thought on the Female Labor Force

María Valentina Vargas

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Universidad Sergio Arboleda

Traditionally, it has been argued that men's physical strength made them better suited as hunters and warriors, while women were primarily devoted to gathering and child-rearing. However, recent research has revealed that women also played an active role in hunting in primitive societies (BBC, 2023).

The historical narrative has tended to undervalue the capabilities and accomplishments of women, relegating their role merely to domestic and caregiving tasks. This has been justified by the presumption of a lack of physical and mental abilities, which restricted the self-determination of many women and prevented them from assuming economic or labor responsibilities outside the home.

This phenomenon raises a crucial question: how has economic thought influenced female participation in the principal economic spheres, and what has been the true historical role of women—a role that has been systematically erased by traditional approaches to history?

As early as 370 BCE, Plato engaged in his dialectical method with the established gender roles of the polis, questioning both their applicability and the differences between the sexes:

Do we expect the female guardians to join in keeping watch over what the male guardians guard, to hunt with them, and share all their activities? Or do we expect them to remain indoors, incapacitated by childbirth and the nursing of young, while the males work and have all the care of the flock? —They share all things in common—said he—except that we treat the females as weaker and the males as stronger. —Is it possible, then—said I—to employ any creature for the same purposes as another if you do not assign it the same upbringing and education? —It is not possible. —If, therefore, we are to use women for the same tasks as men, we must also teach them the same things. —Yes. (Plato, 1969, Book 5)

However, the predominant vision in the Western world over the past millennia regarding the female role was the Aristotelian one, implemented by the Catholic Church and the Scholastics following the translation and assimilation of the Greek philosopher's manuscripts by theologians such as Thomas Aquinas in his *Summa Theologica*, Albertus Magnus, and John Duns Scotus. Aristotle, in his work *Politics*, asserts: 'The male, unless constituted in some way contrary to nature, is by nature more expert in leadership than the female...' (Aristotle, 1957). These ideas, combined with the guilt assigned to woman in the biblical story of Genesis, had a profound impact on the collective imaginary regarding women's roles, casting them as the weaker sex that succumbed to temptation and therefore needed to be subjected to male protection.

For example, during the Middle Ages, when a girl married, her husband gained control over her interests and acted as responsible for her conduct, which is why women are not mentioned as frequently as men in legal matters. In cases of infraction, the husband, not the wife, was held

accountable. Power (1996, as cited in Mark, 2019) writes that 'the great majority of women lived and died unrecorded while they worked in the fields, on the farm, and in the home.'

Power notes that despite the view of women as second-class citizens—which appears in sermons and other ecclesiastical works—household records, guild archives, and other select documents show that women, throughout most of the Middle Ages, earned their living in the same trades as men.

During the medieval period, lower-class women were bakers, brewers, dairymaids, chambermaids, craftswomen, weavers, and above all, tenant farmers who worked in the fields alongside their husbands and children. They frequently took charge of a business upon their husband's death—especially during the Black Death—and were valued as traders, artists, and craftswomen.

Nevertheless, the concept of woman as cheap labor was well established from the feudal system and was perpetuated through the guild system, as women were not considered legal entities and therefore typically earned less than men. (Mark, 2019)

This factor, however, did not encourage female participation in the guilds, as men felt threatened by the prospect of job loss and retaliated by restricting guild work exclusively to their own sex. This situation, combined with the prohibition of adequate education for women—being barred from attending university, or even from having literate nuns (Mark, 2019)—and the inability to own property, had repercussions for their inclusion in the labor force, leaving them with limited options for generating their own income.

At the end of the eighteenth century, the Industrial Revolution transformed the labor situation for both men and women. While the home had previously been the center of production and family life, industrialization shifted the workplace from the home to the factory. Yet it was not until the mid-nineteenth century that the male breadwinner role emerged, with women assuming most domestic tasks. This transition is attributed to a growing humanitarian protest against the harsh treatment of women and children at the onset of the Industrial Revolution, who continued to face lower wages. (Fernández, 2018)

Consequently, British legislation raised the minimum age for child labor in factories, established limits on working hours, and prohibited certain forms of heavy labor for women. In this way, women became primarily devoted to domestic tasks while men went out to work. Being the sole household provider reinforced the traditional position of the man as head of the family, as well as the subordination of women. (Kranzberg & Hannan, 2023)

Despite the rapid social and technological changes of the era, the position of women remained bound to an ancient pattern of dependence on father, husband, sons, or brothers, which prevented them from accessing higher education, suffrage, property ownership, child custody after divorce, or the freedom to choose their own path, due to culturally accepted gender roles. These roles kept women away from public life and the labor sphere. On the female condition, John Stuart Mill wrote in his essay *The Subjection of Women* (1869): 'How women were treated.—Unlimited extension of paternal authority.—The crime of petty treason.—The wife a slave.—She has no right to her own property.—She is more a slave than any slave has ever been.' (Mill, 2012)

The archetype of the ideal woman as mother, wife, and homemaker—in need of male protection due to her physical and mental incapacity—was a powerful idea in nineteenth-century society.

Accordingly, Mill critiques the argument that women are naturally less competent, maintaining that it is simply unknown what women are capable of, because they have never been permitted to try; no authoritative declaration can be made without evidence.

I deny that anyone knows, or can know, the nature of the two sexes, as long as they have only been seen in their present relation to one another. Until conditions of equality exist, no one can assess the natural differences between women and men, distorted as they have been. What is natural to the two sexes can only be found out by allowing both to develop and use their faculties freely. (Mill, 2012)

Consequently, Mill argues that if society truly wishes to understand what is genuinely natural in gender relations, it must establish a free market for all the services women perform, guaranteeing equitable remuneration for their contributions to collective well-being. Only in such a context would the practical decisions of women be more likely to reflect their genuine interests and abilities.

In line with his utilitarian conception—which remains relevant to this day—John Stuart Mill justifies gender equality by arguing that such equality would generate benefits both for individual women and for society as a whole. According to him, society would benefit by doubling the quantity of mental faculties available for human progress, since the potential and ideas of half the population would be liberated, with a significant impact on human development.

In addition to these arguments, Mill considered that the emancipation and education of women would also have positive effects for men. In his view, female competition and the companionship of equally educated individuals would stimulate greater intellectual development for all. He criticizes the negative influence of constant cohabitation with an uneducated spouse, and maintains that men and women marry primarily to conform to social norms, resulting in a merely domestic relationship. He therefore postulates that by emancipating women, they would be better equipped to establish intellectual connections with their spouses, thereby improving the quality of marital relationships.

He likewise defends the need to reform matrimonial legislation, proposing a model in which marriage constitutes a contractual agreement that imposes no restrictions on either party. His proposals include modifying inheritance laws to allow women to retain their own property and to work outside the home, thereby achieving economic independence.

In this context, Mill also addresses the question of female suffrage, arguing that since women represent half of the population, they must also have the right to vote, as public policies directly affect them. Finally, the theorist highlights that even in societies with as pronounced an inequality as England and Europe, evidence can already be found that, when given the opportunity, women can excel, citing queens such as Elizabeth I and Victoria of England, or the French patriot Joan of Arc, arguing that if granted the opportunity, women will distinguish themselves in other fields and must have the possibility of attempting to do so.

Correspondingly, multiple socialist currents of thought, with strong utilitarian overtones, questioned the patriarchal ideology and the female condition, resulting in egalitarian and syndicalist postulates such as those of Beatrice and Sidney Webb, evidenced in Fabian socialism, as well as in the more widely known Marxist feminism, whose origins lie in the analysis of gender oppression carried out by Friedrich Engels in his work *The Origin of the Family, Private Property,*

and the State (1884). Engels argues that the subordination of women is not a consequence of their biological disposition, but of social relations. He affirms that men's efforts to achieve control over women's labor and sexual faculties have been gradually solidified and institutionalized in the nuclear family.

From a Marxist historical perspective, Engels analyzes the generalized social phenomena associated with female sexual morality, such as the fixation on virginity and sexual purity, the criminalization and violent punishment of women who commit adultery, and the demands for women's submission to their husbands. Ultimately, Engels traces these phenomena back to the development of exclusive control over private property by the patriarchs of the propertied class, and the desire to ensure that their inheritance is transmitted only to their own descendants.

Continuing with the idea of female emancipation from the socialist framework, in the final decades of the nineteenth century and the early twentieth century, women such as Clara Zetkin, Eleanor Marx, and Alexandra Kollontai championed a proletarian revolution that would overcome as many inequalities between men and women as possible. A policy of solidarity was thus considered the means to carry out a socialist platform. In contrast to feminism, Marxist feminists supported a more radical political program to liberate women through socialist revolution, with special emphasis on work among women and on materially changing their conditions following the revolution. (Stokes, 2000)

The application of these socialist ideas became evident following the Russian Revolution of 1917, with Vladimir Lenin speaking of the importance of liberating women from domestic tasks so that they could participate more fully in society (Goldberg, 2017). An effort was thereby initiated to remunerate workers for household tasks. The principle of 'equal pay for equal work' was officially legislated. Furthermore, some changes were implemented with respect to the traditional emphasis on the family, such as facilitating divorce and granting full rights to children born outside of wedlock. (Engel, 2004)

In brief, the development of female participation throughout history has been influenced by an intersection of ideas stemming from diverse philosophical and political fields. From the reflections of Aristotle in ancient Greece to the feminist and socialist visions of the nineteenth and twentieth centuries, various currents of thought have contributed to questioning and transforming gender roles.

The ideas of thinkers such as John Stuart Mill, who advocated for gender equality from a utilitarian perspective, highlighted the need to expand women's opportunities and rights within society. Mill argued that female emancipation would not only benefit women individually, but would also enrich human progress by fully leveraging the potential and abilities of half the population.

Furthermore, the socialist currents, influenced by figures such as Engels, Kollontai, the Webbs, and Lenin, framed the struggle for gender equality as an integral part of the struggle for social justice and the emancipation of the working class.

Together, these ideas provided a conceptual and political framework for challenging patriarchal power structures and promoting gender equality. This momentum became especially evident following the World Wars, when women assumed labor roles previously reserved for men, playing a crucial role in industrial production as well as in the economy and politics.

Through critical reflection and collective action, significant advances have been achieved in expanding women's opportunities and rights. Nevertheless, work remains to be done to achieve full equality across all spheres of society.

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